

1 **CDKN control by UBE3D.**

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6 Cyclin dependent kinase inhibitors, encoded by CDKN genes, function as endogenous inhibitors of the cell
7 cycle. Cancer is defined by unrestricted cell division. Activation of CDKN genes would serve as ideal
8 cancer therapeutics. As inhibitors rather than activating small molecules are currently most widely
9 pursued for therapeutic targeting, we searched for inhibitors of CDKN genes in order to identify cellular
10 encoded CDKN inhibitors for small molecule CDKN inhibitor blockade to activate CDKN genes. We
11 describe here the identification of ubiquitin E3 ligase UBE2D as an endogenous inhibitor of CDKN genes
12 in human cancer.
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We performed whole transcriptome transcriptional co-regulation analysis to discover genes co-regulated with CDKN2A for CDKN inhibitor identification, by querying total transcription in multiple tissues. We identified the ubiquitin E3 ligase UBE3D as a CDKN co-regulated gene product (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1: CDKN2A, which encodes for two central and evolutionary conserved tumor suppression molecules - p16INK4A and p14ARF - is transcriptionally co-regulated with E3 ligase UBE3D.

Rank	Query Gene	Entrez ID	Coexpress. Score	p-value	Description
	CDKN2A	1029	-3.2000	0.0032	cyclin-dependent kinase inhibitor 2A
1274	UBE3D	90025	0.6037	0.0389	ubiquitin protein ligase E3D

UBE3D transcriptome-wide percent co-regulation: 1274/17858 total genes: 92.9%

To evaluate proof of concept experimentally, we measured total transcription following depletion of UBE3D in MDA-MB-231 triple negative breast cancer cells *in vitro*. Depletion of UBE3D, mimicking chemical inhibition of its ligase function, resulted in CDKN activation (**Figure 2**).

n=3 MDA-MB-231

n=3 MDA-MB-231 with UBE3D depletion

Figure 2: Depletion of UBE3D in triple negative breast cancer cells results in activation of CDKN2C and CDKN3.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
1033	2.34e-09	0.1158	-5.9725272	-6.92e-01	774.57	CDKN3	868/18496	95.3
1031	1.82e-06	0.1075	-4.7721086	-5.13e-01	749.23	CDKN2C	1432/18496	92.3

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Discussion

We identified here using systems biological methods UBE3D as an endogenous inhibitor of cyclin dependent kinase inhibitors (CDKNs). CDKN activation by UBE3D small molecule inhibition is a viable therapeutic strategy in humans with solid tumors.

Methods

We used GSE189423 for this measurement of total transcription in cultured triple negative breast cancer cells following *in vitro* depletion of MDA-MB-231. We used SEEK (Princeton) for transcriptional co-regulation analysis.